

ISic2933

I.Sicily inscription 2933

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble (grey)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2014.09.09

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Giovanni, excavation 1895

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15551

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493925

EDCS 43400834

Bibliography

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Diehl, Ernst Johann L. 1925. *Inscriptiones Latinae Christianae Veteres*. Berlin. At

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Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 37 no.66

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